

Emerging opportunities for digital fabrication education, the making of the ‘*Caparazón de madera*’ pavilion

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to report on how we integrated a method for manufacturing double curvature surfaces with cold-pressed wooden parts, and how this research and educational experience developed in the form of a pavilion. During the process, we set some goals, reducing costs from previous experiences, with further intricate geometry, configuring an agile assembly and disassembly for the parts, developing an efficient and safe structure, making a visually attractive and apparent simple geometry, with a natural and renewable carbon sequestrant material. We built with enthusiastic participants in a curricular workshop, where they acquired their first or most important experience and significant knowledge in computational design and digital fabrication throughout the making.

Keywords

Double curvature wood, cold press fabrication, digital fabrication, parametric design, pavilion

1 Introduction

This research seeks to answer on how to build an affordable lightweight structure, with double curvature wooden panels with digital design and fabrication while developing as an emerging opportunity for a learning scenario.

The design and construction of a pavilion were commissioned and carried out by teachers and students in less than three months, adaptable to different plazas, and with the complementary goals of reducing costs, trying something new from previous experiences with further intricate geometry, agile in assembly and disassembly, structurally safe and visually attractive. This process was intended to become an emerging opportunity for all the participants to acquire or improve their digital fabrication skills through a curricular workshop which has now become their most important experience in computational design and digital fabrication.

The geometry of this pavilion the ‘*Caparazón de Madera*’ or Wood Carapace can be described as a double-curved wooden surface, composed on the outside of irregular and curved rhombus tiles, with small cuts that allow it to acquire a synclastic shape, and that on the inside is supported by a radial structure based on arches assembled with oblique incisions. The design and manufacturing were carried out with a precision of tenths of millimeters thanks to the digital manufacturing equipment of the Laboratory of

Architecture + Design and Experimental Technology (LATE) of the Faculty of Architecture UNAM. Every participating member became aware of the limitations and solved the difficulties that arose from the confrontation between the idea with a maximum aspiration, the design that foresees the best solution, and the execution, which is always conditioned by reality.

Here, we sought to develop a method for the manufacturing of double curvature surfaces with cold-pressed prefabricated wooden parts. The parts were manufactured in one month to be exhibited as the UNAM representative pavilion at Mextrópoli 2024 for a couple of weeks.

2 Choice of material, wood, a sustainable material

Nowadays any product designed, and in particular Architecture, is obliged to conceive dwelling with deep environmental awareness to reverse the negative effects that are registered through data of the construction industry, which represents more than 34% of energy demand, about 37% of CO₂ emissions and about 9% of total CO₂ emissions related to energy consumption due to the carbon integrated into buildings. This impact can be reduced with alternative materials and decarbonizing conventional materials such as concrete. (UN,2022)

Thus, we have sought to work with natural materials like wood, since it is a renewable, durable, reusable, recyclable, and a compostable alternative. Wood accumulates and prevents the release of CO₂ into the atmosphere, as a building material it uses 40% less energy in its manufacture than conventional materials, up to 75% fewer toxicity emissions into the air and water, it sequesters CO₂ during its growth, and throughout its useful life, its average life is 50 years and at the end of its useful life it can be reused or recycled. (FSC, 2025)

3 Possibilities with wood, double curvature geometry

There are various techniques to fabricate double curved surfaces in wood, such as band saw cutting (Chai et al. 2021), slotting and kerfing plywood sheets (Greenberg & Körner, 2014), steam bending (Ratnasingam et al. 2022), hygromorphic self-shaping gridshell structures (Grönquist et al. 2020), segmented construction (Vestartas et al. 2019), thermoforming (Srinivasan et al. 2007), and active bending (Naboni, 2022).

Wood is a flexible material because microscopically, the cells that support mechanical tissues appear as elongated cellulose cells linked by lignin (UPV, 2023). It is possible to curve pieces of wood mainly using 3 different low-cost methods:

Steam · Heating the wood with high temperature, and steam humidity up to 99 degrees Celsius, causes the lignin to lose strength and makes the piece of wood malleable,

Glued laminates · Wood is curved by joining individual segments of wood with a smaller flexible section using industrial-type adhesives and pressure with the help of presses and/or molds,

Kerfing · In this method, spaced and oriented cuts are made according to the type of curvature required in the section of the wood with full or partial depth, allowing it to bend without the need for machinery. (Souza, 2020)

4 Parametric design

We consider fundamental for this design the optimization of processes with the most accessible and advanced digital computational design tools, specifically with parametric design with Grasshopper since it is possible to generate an integrated workflow thanks to the wide variety of digital tools that can be used simultaneously and comprehensively in an algorithm with real-time visualization with the use of native components and contributed by the community. (Robert McNeel And Associates,2025)

5 Digital manufacturing

Digital manufacturing, through Computer Numerical Control (CNC) tools, reduces costs and production times, improving productive performance between 10% and 100%. Digital factories achieve increases in production, manufacturing capacity, and labor productivity through digital twins, essential with the use of this technology, that allow processes to be simulated and analyzed, and guarantee safety and compliance with specifications. (Ruíz, 2020)

Although this technology has come to be perceived as a threat that will replace labor because manual manufacturing is deeply embedded, specialized, and profitable in some sectors, we agree that digital manufacturing require an understanding of local resources and challenges. (Tovar, 2023) Depending on the resources and capabilities of a fabrication laboratory such as our own, it was determined to use pine plywood and MDF for building a press and only pine plywood boards for the pavilion, which works better structurally wise, although other woods would have worked better under the rain. We selected these materials according to the available economic resources and how accessible these materials would be for acquisition in Mexico City, the standardized dimensions (2.44 x 1.22 meters) were helpful since they can be processed in most of the work areas in the available subtractive manufacturing tools, CNC milling and Laser Cutting.

Usually, the combination of inputs and precision tools contributes to generating proposals with more controlled precision and dismantling different opportunities for error related to the interpretation of documentation, while the file of routes for cuts and engravings is processed from the digital file directly from the original geometry.

6 Pavilion, project-based learning

At the intersection between computational design, digital fabrication, architecture, design, and experimentation is the Laboratory of Architecture+Design and Experimental Technology (LATE) which is a space that articulates research, learning, dissemination, performance evaluation, and the application of the latest available technology, for the benefit of the creative and productive processes of the disciplines of the UNAM Faculty of Architecture. (Bolaños, 2016)

According to the fabrication capabilities of our lab, for this pavilion, in addition to testing the original integration of geometries and processes, we oriented this process to generate significant learning in the application of pre-existing knowledge for the generation of new knowledge with mainly practical processes, divided and delegated according to the capabilities of each team member in search of achieving the objective promptly.

The educational strategy developed here articulates project-based learning as a teaching method, which is developed collaboratively and exposes students to situations that promote formulating proposals for a specific problem. Here students are involved in their learning process and develop skills such as problem-solving and teamwork with completely real and tangible determinants (PUCP, 2025) the tutors gave the outlines of the project, explained the geometry, the process involved, advised on structural loads, and determined the main methodology for building the pavilion. The more advanced participants served as student leaders and designed constructive details while helping others with lesser experience to understand the process and advice on the specific actions for developing details of constructive elements and fabricating processes.

Since the pavilion commission arrives just before the vacation period, the design proposals of these pavilions are usually developed by the academics, and the exercise is configured as a practical workshop with the students looking for a constructive, production and assembly solution, where the participants, students and teachers, propose, design and develop under supervision and follow the tutors' recommendations.

Every participant can understand better not only the digital processes but also the timing involved in designing fabricating and assembling, logistics for installation and dismantling, documenting the process, and other actions related.

7 Design Methodology

Based on previous experiences with the generation of plywood structures with simple curvature, in particular with the pavilion created for Mextrópolis 2022 (Arellano, 2022), it was decided to combine this type of bending with 'kerfing' techniques or small cuts that allow us to bend the wood with double curvature. Considering this as a first experience in manufacturing with double curvature under the capabilities of LATE, it was decided to opt for a sphere section for the pavilion as a synclastic geometry that would allow the manufacturing of all the parts to be expedited with a single press within the available time.

The radius of the geometry would be rounded to an integer number when negotiating between an ideal number of parts and a maximum fabrication size, of each of these, inscribed within the cutting capabilities of our equipment. The parts to be assembled within the three planned days of assembly had to be kept in a double-digit quantity, which on the one hand would have to be the smallest possible number to facilitate transportation and assembly, although, on the other hand, there would have to be the largest number of pieces to be configured to achieve a geometrical texture instead of a perceived assembly of a few number of parts that could be counted with the fingers, for the benefit of greater visual quality. Therefore, the number of parts to which the design would have to be addressed was between 20 and 40.

Each part should be kept below 20 kg since for several projects we have considered it the maximum weight that any person should be able to carry. (ISO 11228-1: 2021)

The useful area of our project aspired to be the largest and a sphere radius of 3m was thus defined. In the first evaluation, we sought to reduce the number of parts beyond those that would be left out when considering a door. Therefore, it was decided to section the project with different cuts so that at the same time it would be possible to separate from the idealistic configuration of the sphere in a parallel search for an increase in the complexity of the details to be resolved. So in negotiation with the number of parts and the size, the design progressed by sectioning with a plane that crossed vertically the radius of the sphere, to leave out half a dome, another plane also vertical although with a different angle, was separated from the center with a uniform distance to tangentially section the sphere, and a third and last incision composed of a straight cut and a curve determined by the structural grid was also subtracted.

The structural grid was explored with geodesic lines although it was determined to use arcs to generate supports made from flat plywood boards. On the other hand, the structural grid was determined as radial and diagonal, so that irregular rhombuses would be generated. The work with arches and the distance between them made it possible to minimize the obliquity that would arise from the ribs that would come off from here. By playing with the number of elements, the possible overlap, and the incisions in the sphere that, due to their variety, demanded a wide range of technical solutions, it was decided to discretize the pavilion with 46 pieces, which in turn would consist of three layers each. These would be superimposed on a tile-like structure to facilitate manufacturing precision, simplify assembly precision, and absorb the deformations to which the pavilion would be subject depending on a varying location. On the other hand, the tiles overlap would absorb deformations depending on the amount of humidity to which it would be subject.

By having pieces like curved tiles needed to be manufactured with flat boards, we configured each tile with three layers of three-millimeter pine plywood, with an algorithmic method of planarization by arcs and distances that had to be developed and that allowed the cutting of the pieces in real magnitude before the pressing process.

Different patterns and sizes of interior cuts or notches were tested, which also had to determine the productive feasibility within the established times.

To prevent water seepage, the two outer layers of the tiles were cut with a pattern of triple straight radial line notches, while for the middle layer, a new pattern was developed with a triple curved radial line that fits right in the middle of the other pattern. This new pattern was interspersed in the solid parts of the wood left by the outer patterns so that each tile made up of three layers could be waterproof by having complementary patterns.

An edge pattern was also developed that helped prevent segments of each part from being detached by cutting the notches.

Figure 1: Discretization of parts, layout for the smallest piece. R. Bolaños 2024

8 Press Design, Manufacturing, and Assembly

The dimensions of the press were sought as large as the parts cut from a 2.44x1.22m board would allow, which when incorporating the sphere section, the thickness of the lamellae and its corresponding lid, would be 0.43m high, approximately one-fifth of the length of the board.

It was decided to develop a waffle structure with plywood and MDF in order to lighten the parts of the press, to be operated by two people when entering or removing pieces. The press should be able to admit the largest elements resulting from discretization. It would have notches on the outside for easy opening and to accommodate medium-sized presses available in the laboratory.

Parametric Model

The use of computational design and a parametric model was crucial in solving the press due to the specifications and variations between the elements. The system consisted of 4 waffles: an upper and lower one in 3mm MDF and an upper and lower one in 15mm plywood. The MDF waffles had 66 pieces (21 longitudinal and 45 transverse) with a constant spacing and height of 5cm, while the plywood waffles had 10 pieces (3 longitudinal and 7 transverse) with a constant spacing of 25cm and variable height. The press, with a volume of 2.40x1.10x0.43m, was divided by a curvature defined by a sphere of 3m radius. Thanks to the parametric model in Grasshopper, the necessary modifications and tolerances could be managed in real-time, generating more than 152 different parts with a reference nomenclature for assembly achieved in less than 2 weeks.

For the milling process, the same cutting algorithm was used and post-processed with VCarve, where the external profiling was configured in 15mm plywood milled in 3 layers of 5mm, following the criterion of not milling to a depth greater than the diameter of the milling cutter in this case of 6.35mm. This process required less than 2 days to complete.

Figure 2: Wood press. Photo: R. Bolaños. 2024.

9 Manufacturing of roof tiles

Testing the patterns, the pattern design, and the corresponding algorithms, took less than a week and a half.

The joining of the layers previously manufactured for the tiles was carried out by gluing the layers, placing adhesive tape on the edges to avoid unwanted gaps between layers, and placing them inside the already assembled press to clamp with clamps (presses) on the edges for 4 hours, a recommended time for the adhesive to dry. The pieces were then removed from the press to be waterproofed with the material donated for this task by Stone Prime. This process along with the cutting process took 2 weeks.

Figure 3: Final kerfing test with 3 layers and final pattern size. Photo: B. Velazquez. 2024

10 Design, Manufacturing, and Pre-assembly of the Structure

The development of the structure was carried out by a digital twin using algorithms. It began by defining the border lines and the oblique segmentation lines without overlap to convert them into 36 ribs, half with a clockwise inclination and the other half counterclockwise. Each line defined a coplanar plane to generate surfaces with a superelevation of 15 cm.

The small lateral holes in the tiles destined for attachment were projected onto the segmentation curves, using them to locate where the perforations should go in the ribs. Subsequently, the surfaces with these perforations acquired a thickness of 18 mm, resolving the intersections with a waffle-type assembly system. 41 intersections were identified, worked in the plane of each rib to generate rectangular prisms that contained 3D obliquities and, using Boolean operations, and 2D orthogonal projection of the inlet and outlet of the perforation of the intersecting rib, it was possible to manufacture the necessary notches on a 3-axis milling machine (x, y, z) incapable of making angled incisions. Each joint included 4 perforations, two on each intersected rib to secure it with Velcro tape and zip ties for a quick assembly and disassembly process.

Finally, the ribs were divided by considering if the largest dimension of each part exceeded 2.44m (limit of the plywood board) to facilitate assembly. At each segmentation point, splices were generated by dividing the thickness of the material to ensure alignment and union with screws. These joints were designed on the same face to optimize milling without the need to rotate the part, minimizing precision errors.

The process of dismantling the structure generated with an algorithm involved the handling of a total of 51 pieces, each one with a different plane of inclination and orientation. A process of reorientation of the pieces on an xy plane was generated with the position of the splices facing up. Subsequently, the necessary 2D curves were extracted for processing in VCarve, optimizing the use of material to the maximum. In addition, a nomenclature was incorporated for each piece that indicated which element it belonged to. This process along with the design process took a total time of less than 2 weeks.

Finally, the milling was carried out with the use of seven 18mm plywood boards to later be waterproofed with the use of an air gun for dispensing coating layers, this took just under a week. To identify previous errors and speed up the assembly, we sought to pre-assemble the 6 sections into which the structure was divided. This took approximately 20 hours of continuous work, prior to a long holiday.

Figure 4: 3D subdivided digital twin and 2D cutting into 2.44x1.22 meter boards for CNC milling. Image: B. Velazquez. 2024.

11 Assembly in Plaza de Santo Domingo

Assembly was carried out in 2 days. The first day the parts and tools were transported to the site, but due to transportation limitations, it was necessary to disassemble the pre-assembled sections. It was decided to reassemble the sections on site and protect them from the rain.

On the second day, all the parts were assembled, aligning the major arch with a line parallel to the pan coupe of the Medicine Palace. Sergeants were used to present the pieces, make adjustments and screw. The process progressed in parallel, assembling rib joints and edge arches from the bottom up, leaving, in the end, the major crown, stabilized with spacers, and the minor crown, resolved with rope.

Figure 5: Inauguration in Plaza de Santo Domingo. Photo: R. Bolaños. 2024.

12 Discussion and Results

The development of the pavilion took a total of three months, with two months dedicated to the development of the bending method, including the design of the bending pattern system, tests, manufacture of the press, base shape and segmentation with oblique cuts, and one month for the manufacture of the structure, the press and the tiles, carrying out processes in parallel, resulting in a roof area of 10.6 m², with a maximum span of 6 m, 3 m maximum height and a weight of approximately 200 kg.

The process allowed a full academic hands-on workshop where three teachers, three advanced student leaders, and other fifteen participants gained knowledge in digital fabrication, computational design, logistics, and structure-building techniques with great results.

Figure 6: Educational, design, and fabrication process participants. Photo: R. Bolaños. 2024.

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